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The Royals Write Back: Khwaja Hasan Nizami's *Tears of the Begums* as a Denotative Testimonio

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Abstract:

In the aftermath of the revolt of 1857, the offended and cautious British introduced a series of stringent measures to alter and erase the collective memory of the colonized Indian people, in an effort to ensure that no organized rebellion occurs in the future. The reign of terror that ensued sought its justification in the accounts of British historians, who branded this rebellion as the “Sepoy Mutiny.” These narratives were further reinforced by a scarcity of genuine efforts among Indians to contest them until well after the nation’s independence.

Khwaja Hasan Nizami’s *Tears of the Begums* (originally in Urdu) is a different case, though. Written in the 1910s and 1920s, it documents the testimonies of members of the royal family, who bore the brunt of the cruellest aspects of this domination. The collection of twenty-nine accounts of decolonized history makes this text worthy of being cited as an earlier example of testimonial literature or *testimonio*.

The present paper aims to discuss the prospects and problems of situating it within this Latin American genre by studying it against the ideas of prominent testimonial writing scholars such as George Yúdice, John Beverley, and Kavita Panjabi, finding reverberations of features considered indispensable for categorizing it in this genre.

Keywords: Revolt of 1857, Testimonial literature, Tears of the Begums, Colonial memory erasure, Decolonized history, Resistance literature, Sepoy Mutiny, Historiography.

Introduction

“History isn’t the lies of the victors, as I once glibly assured Old Joe Hunt; I know that now. It’s more the memories of the survivors, most of whom are neither victorious nor defeated”

Julian Barnes p.56

That history is the lies of the victors is no longer a contested statement today. History abounds with examples of narratives validated by the winning side and passed off as facts unless the vanquished side speak up for themselves. After WW II the prevalent interpretation had imperial Japan blamed for causing the war until revisionist historians, notably Charles Tansil and Frederic Sanborn disputed it by arguing that America too was to be blamed for pressing the Japanese too hard in 1940 (see Tansill,1952; Sanborn, 1951). Examples can also be cited about historians dismantling the popular views concerning the Vietnam war (1955-75) (Lewy ,1978).

This pattern in historiography is evident in the Indian scenario in the events pertaining to the uprising of 1857 and its aftermath. The Revolt that started with a number of Indian soldiers refusing to follow their English commanders' order of using a specific kind of cartridge culminated in a full-scale war between the colonizers and the colonised for a period of five months between May and September ,1857. The resultant victory of the British side assured them a position to decide and define the narrative imposed in history books. As for the Indians, the war, fought under the banner of the Mughal ruler Bahadur Shah Zafar, proved to be the last nail in the coffin of Mughal rule in India.

William Darlymple notes in his book *The Last Mughal* how Governor General Canning took this rebellion as a pretext to end even the nominal presence of the Mughal authority,

“.. to take the dramatic and historic step of deposing the Mughal dynasty, which had ruled northern India for more than three hundred years (135).

The Mughal royal family, some thousand members of it, were ousted in the siege of the Delhi Fort, besides several of them getting arrested and many of Zafar’s sons and grandsons executed in the reign of terror that followed. Major William Ireland notes that twenty-nine sons of the royal house were put to death (1861: 280) This entire set of events was branded and propagated as "Sepoy mutiny " by British historians of that era and the narrative incorporated the ungratefulness of the Indian soldiers in rearing their heads against their masters, highlighting their brutality in killing British civilians and soldiers. SEE, *Henry Mead's The Sepoy Revolt: Its Causes and Consequences*; John W. Kaye, *A History of the Sepoy War in India*.

To counter the possibility of another rebellion against the legal authority the government (now the British Crown exercising administrative control instead of the East India Company) imposed measures to destroy symbols that allowed the formation of a shared identity and collective memory among Indians. William Darlymple cites from the letters written by eminent poet Mirza Ghalib several places of cultural importance having been demolished by the Raj, including Shahjahani buildings, the mosques surrounding the Fort, the Akbarabadi Masjid, Jan Nisar Khan's *Chhatta* and settlements around Jama Masjid, to name a few. Ghalib decries this bulldozing spree,

“When the British destroyed a *Gali* or *Katra* and built a broad and straight road over the debris, they dismantled a centuries old way of life and an entire culture, turning the glorious city of Delhi into a deserted place”. (422)

Cohn calls this process of altering the architecture an intentional 'desacralization' (Cohn 1987:646)

Arshad Islam makes an observation regarding the multiple stringent actions taken by the government forces to ensure no future possibility of rebellion on such scale:

"In the aftermath of The Revolt the British sought to provide a safeguard for their rule in India by killing almost all the potential male members of the Mughal royal family because they knew that in a Muslim society only male members are the breadwinners. When Bahadur Shah's son applied to return to India the British refused to grant permission because they felt that their rule would be threatened by the presence of any immediate member of the erstwhile royal family."(208)

The stringent measures of the colonizers also included burying Bahadur Shah Zafar's body in an unmarked grave in Rangoon where he died after five years of exile. The government anticipated that an identifiable grave would serve as an allegory for the unity of Indians against it. The deliberate attempts for erasing the cultural memory were a way for the Crown to ensure that no platform is provided to the colonised to gain strength and resist the rule. This contestation of narratives was further strengthened by a barrage of publications, some of them as early as in 1858, that appreciated the ideological position of the colonisers.

"In the historiography of the great revolt, the output of published material from the British perspective was so voluminous during the latter half of the nineteenth century that for a long time the dominant colonial narrative of this upheaval remained unchallenged. Until the first decade of the twentieth century there was no major published work from the perspective of the colonized. This, however, is not surprising. Given the ruthlessness with which the revolt was crushed, and the repression that was unleashed by the colonial state in the post-1857 period, any attempt to glorify the revolt was out of the question." (Farooqi, 2023)

The effort to subvert these narratives received its official green signal pretty late in India. It was the first Education Minister Maulana Abdul Kalam Azad who asked historian Surendranath Sen to write a historical account of 1857 from an Indian perspective. But Sen, according to some historians, was not able to achieve the needful. He, in order to spare the

terminologies of political narratives, called his book '1857' instead of the War of independence (as was the Indian narrative) or the mutiny (as was the British point of view). Rudrangshu Mukherjee states that Sen refused to make use of Persian and Urdu narratives for the projects and relied mostly on British narratives. He (Sen) did not document enough accounts of the torments faced by the losing side (2008: 53).

Khwaja Hasan Nizami, born sixteen years after the war, on the other hand, was throwing a wrench into the state sponsored notions. By collecting eyewitness accounts of the victims and publishing them in thin booklets, he was challenging the dominant historiography and allowing for the formation of a collective identity. The text under analysis in this paper is one among many such story collections written in an attempt to correct the Western canon.

An essayist, satirist and journalist, Hasan Nizami, undertook this job of compiling the untold tales of the sufferers of the royal family post 1857 war in twelve books, way back in the first quarter of the twentieth century. *Begumat ke Aansoo* (1922) remains his most popular collection of stories, translated into English by Rana Safvi as *Tears of the Begums* in 2022. It comprises twenty-nine accounts of the survivors from the royalty subjected to hardship in face of their evacuation from the red fort. Safvi, herself an acclaimed historian, mentions in her translator's note about the significance this text carries:

The Uprising of 1857 resulted in wiping out not only the Mughal Empire but a way of life. The cultural catastrophe has not been documented till date. There are references in books such as Ahmed Ali's *Twilight in Delhi* or Mirza Ghalib's *Dastanbuy* and many Urdu accounts of the nineteenth and twentieth century, but much is left unsaid. In that respect, these tragic stories, based according to Khwaja Hasan Nizami on true facts and his personal research and hard work, are an important testimony to the time. This paper is an attempt to situate this text as one of the earlier examples of Testimonial writing.

Definition

Testimonial literature or *Testimonio* as a genre developed and assumed its current meaning in Latin America in 1970's with the publication of a large number of writings concerning the troubled experience of women, in particular, against the backdrop of social inequality. These writings capture the voices of women of the Bolivian mines (*Let Me Speak! Testimony of Domitila, women of the Bolivian mines*, 1978), of women revolutionaries in Nicaragua (*Sandino's Daughters*, 1984), and the more popular Guatemalan Mayan woman, *I, Rigoberta Menchu*, 1984. However, the legitimation of this literary genre came about with Cuba's Cultural Centre the Casa De las America giving literary prize for this genre in 1970. As far as the definition of the same is concerned George Yúdice provides the needful.

“Testimonial writing may be defined as an authentic narrative, told by a *witness* who is *moved to narrate* by the *urgency* of a situation (e.g., war, oppression, revolution, etc.). Emphasising *popular oral discourse*, the witness portrays his or her own *experiences* as an *agent* (rather than as a representative) of a *collective memory* and *identity*. *Truth* is summoned in the cause of *denouncing* a present situation of exploitation and oppression or in *exorcising* and *setting aright* official history.” (italics mine) (17).

In India, testimonial writing is a very recent phenomenon. It is to be traced in the works of Bama and other Dalit writers' autobiography (see Nayar, 2006) or politically marginalised women in India (see Punjabi, 2002). While a generic approach to Dalit narratives may result in justifying the collective self and the activism part, yet the urgency of the situation aspect seems a bit lacking to suit the definition of *Testimonio*. *Tears of the Begums*, on the other hand, does have a violent epoch defining rebellion as the backdrop of the narrative. Moreover, autobiographies still point in the direction of the narrators being self-sufficient in speaking for themselves. The text under analysis has a documentary feel to it as it offers a platform for those who were sidelined by a formidable enemy and could not speak for themselves for all these

years. Hasan Nizami provides 'voices for the voiceless' radically questioning the historiographical versions of the past and aiming to dismantle the 'master narrative' of the colonizer, lending this whole project a postmodernist stance (see, Gugelberger and Kearney, 1991; and Lyotard, 1984).

Narratives of exploitation and violence

One only has to study Rigoberta Menchu's horrifying account of the torcher and mutilation of her mother against the narrators of *Tears of the Begums* to find parallels. In 'The Accursed Princess' Sultan Bano, granddaughter of Bahadur Shah Zafar recounts the day the emperor was arrested at Humayun's tomb.

" A white man shot my *chachajaan* Mirza Abu Bakr Bahadur. Mirza Sohrab ran towards the White man with a naked sword, but he was shot down by his comrade ...I stood there mute and still as a statue watching it all (page 26). Similar accounts of those displaced from their homes are available. The real hardship faced by these people when they were refused shelters by their own relatives residing in other cities or when they were looted during the journey and left with little or no possession. In "The Real Story of the Destitute Princess " the Princess narrates - "The soldier stopped our palanquin as soon as we came out of the Dilli Darwaza and wanted to arrest my brother. My brother defended himself with his sword and wounded one officer. But he was attacked from all sides and badly wounded. Unable to hold off any longer, he fell off his horse face down on to the ground. Two sharp stones pierced his eyes. My brother died a painful death. "(91-92)

Almost all the stories have similar tales of inhuman atrocity faced by the members of the royal family either directly at the time of their evacuation from the two forts, now captured by the British forces, or indirectly in the years that followed when these innocent people lived in penury. Having been habituated of living a luxurious life, not many could endure the sudden

peripeteia. Some died on their way to other cities, few others lived taking up menial jobs as the last resort. The chapter "The Beggar Prince" documents the testimony of the emperor's real grandson, Mirza Qamar Sultan, now old and blind, who begs at night on the same road where people once bent low to salute him when he rode through the street. (39)

Collective identity

Yúdice in the aforementioned essay lays down the role of the editor/transcriber as being politically committed or empathetic. The interlocutor amplifies the marginalized voices and is sometimes seen standing with the victims. In "The Prince Becomes a Sweeper" Khwaja Hasan Nizami narrates his encounter with a sweeper who is revealed to be a close relative of the emperor of Delhi - a Timurid Prince. He records his reaction:

"The extreme agitation and restlessness I felt on hearing this was more than what a Russian would have felt on hearing about the execution of the Tsar. That was the news of the death, and it was over. This was the news of life which I could not expect to end anytime soon."(110)

Khwaja Hasan Nizami was empathetic to the turmoil of these innocent people and continued to think of them as part of a hierarchically superior royal ancestry. He admits having begun remembering the sweeper with his original title Sahib-e-Alam as all Mughal princes were addressed while the dynasty was flourishing. The memory of their heyday and constant reminder of them being the descendants of Timur, actually helped these victims in getting through their struggles. A sense of collective identity is formed around the history of a powerful lineage. "The Orphan Princes Miserable Eid" has another Prince narrating his mother's pain when right after the revolt was suppressed the son was imprisoned and her husband killed on orders of government "Ya Allah! My heart will burst. Someone please asks Akbar or Shah Jahan to come from the graves and see the distress of this destitute and helpless woman from their family. Someone should tell them my story."(55)

The narrators record their plight but in a collective voice. Their suffering is the suffering of all members of the royal family. George Yúdice states that in all major works of testimonial writing the "... personal story is a shared one with the community to which the testimonial Ista belongs. The speaker does not speak for or represent a community but rather performs an act of identity formation which is simultaneously personal and collective (15). John Beverley opines that "each individual *testimonio* evokes an absent polyphony of other voices, other possible lives and experience (one common formal variation on the first person singular *testimonio* is the polyphonic *testimonio* made up of accounts by different participants in the same event.") (Beverley,2008:573) All testimonial writings talk about a group facing injustice and domination irrespective of the number of narrators interviewed. Svetlana Alexievich's *The unwomanly face of war* (1985) falls in the category of second type with multiple narrators who happen to be the victims of the same force and same event. Evidently, *Tears of the Begums* resembles the later variant that Beverley talks about.

Activism and oppositional stance

That which was supposed to be kept at bay by Britishers' desperate attempt to destroy the cultural artifacts, eliminate the rebel princes and in keeping the grave of the emperor unmarked was attempted to be reinforced by Khwaja Hasan Nizami's effort in collecting these testimonies that not only talked about the victimization and witch hunt of their community but also inspired a strong sense of belongingness and a shared cultural identity. We often find his narrators talking about their grit and determination in face of all odds- all for the sake of a glorious past identity. In "The Prince Becomes a Sweeper", it has been told about the children of the sweeper Prince - "children of a *conquering race* never feel shy of working hard to earn a living" (italics mine). (111)

The account of "The Prince Who Drove a Cart" has an actual testimonial in the court of the titular prince who confesses to have assaulted two persons who had whipped him:

"The blood that runs inside me has now become used to being abused, oppressed and beaten up, but it was not always so. From where the judge sits today, I have ordered the punishment of several rebels and criminals. My heart and mind haven't forgotten those days, even though my eyes have not seen them for eternity. How could I tolerate being whipped?" (73)

It is their sheer memory fuelling and lifting their spirit up and keeping their self-respect intact. The same collective memory targeted by the Britishers and safeguarded by Khwaja Hasan Nizami. This battle of books is a kind of tug of war between the two parties, a kind of war for memories, survival of culture and establishment of narratives.

Therefore, *Tears of the Begums*, a cultural representation formed on the margins of the colonial situation, can be seen as a form of political activism done on the part of Hasan Nizami who reportedly had to face a ban on his book by the British government during the first world war. The ban went on for a decade and half until Sir Malcolm Hailey lifted it (as noted in the twelfth edition). Meriting a ban in itself speaks volumes of the author's anti-colonial stand. Barbara Harlow has already termed testimonial narratives a key form of *Resistance Literature*. (1987)

Problems

One of the things contestable in *Tears of the begum* being compared to other known *testimonios* is that it talks about an event in the past. Hasan Nizami started collecting the tales five decades after the *Ghadar* and hence much after the revengeful motives of the government lost its intensity. Unlike, *I, Rigoberta Menchu* *Tears of the begum* could not set about any real course of action against the hegemonic rule. Menchu, to the contrary, became a political icon after the book became popular and went on to receive the Nobel Prize. But this, in fact, makes

her narrative cease to be that of a subaltern. Beverley calls her *testimonio* a performative one- that which brings about real-life changes, yet in the process does away with the subalternity. In the case of *Tears of the Begums* the voices of the women living on the fringe, double marginalised -one for their gender and another for being identified as the member of the family facing the charges of treason, strengthen the case of an authentic expression of subaltern. And as far as the question of it not being a performative *testimonio* goes we may call it a denotative one.

Another questionable feature of the work is whether it summons the 'truth' because one of the aspects of testimonial writing is its claim for 'truth' in place of political agenda. Rana Safvi lays down the limitations of such accounts as having contradictions with in. She also brings to fore Khwaja taking help of a fictionalised narrative as a vehicle to tell the stories he heard. Given the fact that Khwaja Hasan Nizami was as much of a writer as a journalist, he may well have been concocting stories around the victims' actual testimonies. In defence one may hark back to the basic definition of the self of the narrator having a collective identity. "The point is that the collective experience/ knowledge of a community can, by extension, inhere integrally in its individual members too. For example, was not the fear and terror experienced by hundreds of Muslim women raped in Gujarat in 2002, also by extension the experience of every Muslim woman in Gujarat- even if she has not been raped?" (Panjabi, 2004). Along the same lines we may open ourselves up for aesthetic truth instead of going for the factual one. That these kinds of violence were possible with the victims looking for safe havens cannot be dismissed. Khwaja Hasan Nizami, as Safvi herself writes, told stories rooted in fact, only the tool he used was of a fictionalized narrative. Also, his interviewees had suffered immense trauma and were old, so they cannot be expected to remember everything perfectly.

Conclusion

Kavita Panjabi in her acclaimed essay “Transcultural Politics and Aesthetics: Testimonial Literature” lays down a comprehensive description about what qualifies as a *Testimonio*:

It narrates history but is distinct from historiography in terms of its foregrounding of hitherto silenced voices, *and* its nurturing of collective identity and consciousness; it is not autobiography in that it comprises eye-witness accounts of *collective* struggle; and while possessing literary quality in terms of its ability to interweave aesthetic and narrative dimensions, it is not exactly fiction in that it represents lived experience, and does make claims to “truth”(italics not mine)(2004:122).

Evidently, *Tears of the Begums* fulfils all these criteria, though predating the genre by a good fifty years and existing in a cultural context completely poles apart. Focussing on describing the flip side of the events (thus, denotative) that have become accepted facts, the text easily fits in the genre of *testimonio*. The academic space which has frequently taken to resistance narratives demolishing the established conventions as its favourite intention has remained lukewarm to the lone wolf effort put in by this man.

The recent translation of Nizami's work into English sheds light on his relevance today in face of the other marginalized voices speaking up, questioning the hegemonic accounts of history. This just proves that the empire has “written back” many a times but has been silenced or has not been heard properly (see, Ashcroft, Griffiths and Tiffin, 1989). When Khwaja was undertaking this project of collecting narratives of the displaced, suppressed and then forgotten, he was saving an important chapter in the story of the first War of Independence India fought. In his stories and interviews he recorded his narrators' way of life – their culture, their lost pride, their courage, desires they were deprived of and their fight for survival against all odds, so that ,a long way into future when there are no written accounts or museums made for those

who bore the actual brunt of a revolution for freedom, they can be brought back to life through these pages.

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